

Session SD4 - Compiling the earthquake history of the European Mediterranean area Oral presentation

SD4/Tu/O3 - Calibration methods for parameterising earthquakes 1000-1963 from MDPs in Europe

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One of the goals of the the NA4 module - Distributed Archive of Historical Earthquake Data of the EU NERIES project was to re-assess the earthquake parameters from macroseismic data for the strongest ($M \geq 5.8$) historical earthquakes in Europe for the time-window 1000-1963. Three independent methods have been calibrated and applied, i) Bakun and Wentworth, ii) Boxer and iii) MEEP, in a homogeneous way in six areas: Aegean, Iberia, Italy, United Kingdom, Switzerland and European Stable Continental Region (Scandinavia, Belgium, etc.). Lessons have been learnt concerning the calibration process and the application of the three methods to macroseismic data related to historical events. In general, excellent results were obtained for earthquakes with a good amount and distribution of macroseismic data points (MDPs), e.g. post-1800 events. The three methods are intrinsically different; therefore, we cannot expect that they always give the same results, even if the calibrations are good. Looking at the differences, Boxer tends to perform magnitudes and locations better in onshore situations and credible locations for events with small number of MDPs; MEEP tends to perform better for events with small magnitudes, while the Bakun and Wentworth method is the best to provide locations for offshore earthquakes. When applying the three methods to earthquakes with one MDP only, we would expect that results in terms of location and M_w do not diverge. This was not the case, so far. When applied to events with one MDP in the same region, the three methods gave results not always consistent in terms of M_w . In some cases the patterns of the differences were not comparable, showing an intrinsic weakness in the calibration. The results are encouraging, although some problems are still to be explored. The epicentre determinations appear rather successful and not so much regionally dependent, although to date no method is completely successful in distinguishing coastal and offshore events. The magnitude determinations, which come with uncertainty estimates, strongly depend on the regional calibration; in some cases, they largely diverge, and also strongly differ from the values reported by current national catalogues. We believe that what we have learnt might help in reducing such differences, though they do represent also an estimate of the epistemic uncertainty of the process.

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